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The Dynamics of Creative Agency:

Insights from Two Intensive Diary Studies on University Students

Aleksandra Zielińska & Maciej Karwowski

University of Wrocław, Poland

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Aleksandra Zielińska and Maciej Karwowski, Institute of Psychology, University of Wrocław, Dawida 1, 50-527 Wrocław, Poland.

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The authors declare no known conflict of interest. Please address correspondence concerning this article to Aleksandra Zielińska (Aleksandra.Zielinska@uwr.edu.pl) or Maciej Karwowski (Maciej.Karwowski@uwr.edu.pl).

Abstract

Background: Creative processes and actions are driven not only by people's abilities but also by their confidence and readiness to invest effort.

Aims: This intensive, daily-diary investigation (two studies, total $N_{\text{participants}} = 362$, $N_{\text{measurements}} = 8322$ over three and four weeks) explored how students' self-perception (creative confidence) and self-regulation—two aspects of creative agency—shape the likelihood of undertaking creative action.

Samples: Study 1 included 234 university students (5,923 student-day units); Study 2 included 128 university students (2,399 student-day units).

Methods: In Study 1, participants completed daily diary measurements over four weeks, reporting on their creative self-perception and engagement in creative activities. Using dynamic structural equation modeling (DSEM), we analyzed cross-day lagged associations between creative activity and confidence. In Study 2, students completed daily diaries during a three-week creative project while receiving either self-regulation-enhancing prompts (experimental group) or no additional support (control group). Multilevel regression analyses estimated differences in students' creative self-perception and creative engagement resulting from strengthened self-regulation.

Results: Study 1 showed a robust effect of the previous day's creative activity on the next day's confidence, and no effect of confidence on activity. In Study 2, students whose self-regulation was activated reported higher creative confidence and task-specific creative self-efficacy than the control group and engaged more in creative activities in everyday settings.

Conclusions: These findings shed light on the role of perceived agency for creative action and the dynamic interplay of self-beliefs and self-regulation. They also open avenues for developing brief interventions to make creativity more salient in students' everyday in- and out-of-school settings.

Keywords: creative agency; creative self-beliefs; creative self-regulation; wise intervention

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Students' creativity has different faces, from surprising (yet appropriate) test responses or funny signs on classroom walls to provocative questions and insightful solutions for math problems. These small and mundane acts, often referred to as *mini-c* or *little-c* creativity (Kaufman & Beghetto, 2009), are not required to result in great discoveries or eminent achievements, but they reveal much about creativity's role in students' everyday lives and show how it intersects with their development. However, enhancing students' creative abilities might not be sufficient to make them creatively engaged. While critical for success, abilities alone do not guarantee that people will try them out or maintain their interests and efforts in the face of challenges. Indeed, creative potential rarely translates into real-life activity and achievements (Benedek, 2024; Runco et al., 2010; Said-Metwaly et al., 2024).

What, then, makes people more or less eager to engage in creative activities? Recent research highlights the role of motivational and regulatory mechanisms, theorized as elements of creative agency (Beghetto & Karwowski, in press). In this paper, we focus on two such aspects relevant to students' creative functioning. By integrating findings from two intensive daily diary studies, we examine how students' creative confidence and self-regulation contribute to their creative activity in everyday settings. By doing so, we aim to better understand the factors influencing university students' everyday creative engagement.

Creative Agency: The *Why and How* of Creative Action

Engaging in creative activities (aka *creative engagement*) relies on both cognitive abilities and non-cognitive characteristics like motivation and persistence. In creativity literature, key factors driving one's creative engagement are well illustrated with the concept of agency. Echoing the main features of agency for learning (Code, 2020), creative agency represents "the intentional and self-directed capacity to envision and enact new and meaningful actions within the existing constraints of a particular context, which can bring about changes in our lives and the world around us" (Beghetto &

Karwowski, in press). Thus, creative agency is crucial in translating creative potential into creative behavior by strengthening people's propensity to see creative action as a viable and worthwhile option (*envisioning*) and equipping them with the resources needed to pursue it (*enacting*).

Four fundamental aspects were theorized as vehicles of creative agency: creative confidence, centrality, risk-taking, and self-regulation (Beghetto & Karwowski, in press). Among these, the interplay between efficacy beliefs and regulatory mechanisms is essential for initiating and guiding actions (Bandura, 1991, 2001; Frazier et al., 2021; Schunk, 2001). Therefore, the present research focuses on two agentic elements—creative confidence and creative self-regulation—and explores their role in students' everyday creative activity.

Creative Confidence

Creative confidence, or the extent to which people believe in their creative abilities and skills, is a vital predictor of their engagement in creative attempts (Beghetto, 2006; Tierney & Farmer, 2002). Conceptualized under the umbrella of creative self-beliefs (Álvarez-Huerta et al., 2025; Puente-Diaz & Cavazos-Arroyo, 2018), creative confidence energizes one's action by eliciting the "I can" conviction. Such self-perception embodies both context-specific efficacy beliefs (e.g., feeling capable of showing an original and meaningful perspective in a school essay; creative self-efficacy) and a more holistic conviction about one's creative competencies (e.g., considering oneself capable of generating creative ideas and solutions in various situations; creative self-concept). While both are malleable (Anderson & Haney, 2021), creative self-efficacy is more specifically anchored in the task or challenge at hand, being dynamic and future-oriented (Karwowski, Lebuda, et al., 2019). More holistic confidence beliefs are rooted in retrospective judgments of one's general creative experiences, presenting moderate stability, and are sometimes referred to as trait-like creative self-concept (Marsh et al., 2019; Zandi et al., 2022).

Confidence in creative capabilities appears to influence the likelihood of creative outcomes, including more frequent creative activities and improved performances (e.g., Haase et al., 2018). However, these associations were mainly obtained in cross-sectional studies and between-person

analyses. The causal relationships between creative confidence and action have been proposed by Creative Behavior as Agentic Action model (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019). The CBAA views people's confidence as a mediator between their creative potential and activity. Previous studies provide compelling yet initial support for this logic (Choi, 2004; Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019; Zielińska et al., 2021). For instance, a recent daily diary intervention showed that promoting university students' creative confidence with simple prompts increased their engagement in everyday creative activities (Zielińska et al., 2022b).

Yet, what drives confidence? A focal premise of sociocognitive theory posits that (creative) activity, primarily when successful and accompanied by some form of recognition, builds people's confidence (Bandura, 1986). Indeed, prior experiences and achievements are among the most powerful factors influencing people's perceptions of themselves, shaping their sense of agency (Bandura, 2018). However, although most works acknowledge the likely reciprocal links between how people act and what they think about themselves (e.g., Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019; Lebuda et al., 2021; Tierney & Farmer, 2011), not much is known about the hypothesized reciprocal associations and within-person patterns of these relationships. Study 1, presented in this paper, examines these dynamics and investigates the expected reciprocal links between creative confidence and creative activity.

Creative Self-Regulation

Self-regulatory mechanisms employed during creative action, though acknowledged in early works on the creative process (Eindhoven & Vinacke, 1952; Pesut, 1990), have only recently begun to be systematically investigated. More substantial progress has been made in understanding the controllable aspects of creative thought, usually operationalized with brief idea-generation tasks (e.g., Benedek & Jauk, 2018). However, this perspective fails to explain how people approach real-life creative activities. Whether it's more professionalized pursuits or little-c activities students undertake—such as preparing an engaging presentation for science class or decorating a cake for a friend's birthday—effective action relies on planning, monitoring, and adjusting one's cognition,

motivation, and behavior rather than solely relying on ideation strategies (Ivcevic & Nusbaum, 2017). Thus, while creative confidence reveals much about one's perceived agency for creative action, creative self-regulation entails the means to actually exert this action and maintain the efforts.

Several subprocesses of effective self-regulation have been found beneficial for supporting creative activities. These include planning (Liu et al., 2023), perseverance (Lin et al., 2024), metacognitive monitoring and self-judgment (Urban & Urban, 2024), refining task-related goals (Boldt, 2019; Boldt & Kaufman, 2024), and more specific regulatory strategies like mental contrasting (Oettingen et al., 2012). More broadly, self-regulation for creative action encompasses revising and restrategizing, as well as sustaining and maintaining mechanisms (Ivcevic & Nusbaum, 2017). Contextualizing this creativity-tailored perspective within broader self-regulation literature, a recent model (Zielińska et al., 2022a, 2025) applied the Self-Regulated Learning framework (SRL; Zimmerman, 2000, 2002) to highlight how regulatory mechanisms operate across different phases of the creative process (see also Rubenstein et al., 2018). According to this model, navigating creative action involves tactics relevant in the forethought phase: (1) obstacle expectations, and (2) uncertainty acceptance; in the performance phase: (3) adjusting approach, (4) managing ambiguous goals, and (5) emotion regulation and dealing with obstacles; and in the self-reflection phase: (6) improving approach, and (7) readiness for sharing. In essence, creative self-regulation helps people be proactive, goal-driven, mindful of changing circumstances, better at dealing with uncertainties, strategic in their methods, and reflective in their creative endeavors.

Research examining the links between self-regulatory mechanisms and creative performance shows that people exerting regulatory efforts during their pursuits indeed achieve more original and valuable results. Both adolescents (Zielińska et al., 2022a) and teachers (Zielińska, Lebuda, Gop, et al., 2024) who reported more extensive planning, monitoring, adjusting, and self-reflection during long-term projects produced more creative outcomes, as assessed by expert judges. Such regulatory involvement during creative activities can be quite easily activated. A recent experiment (Zielińska, Lebuda, Czerwonka, et al., 2024) utilized brief, open-ended reflective questions inspired by the

prompting procedures used in SRL interventions (e.g., Bannert et al., 2015) to foster self-regulation while working on creative projects: designing a logo, preparing a greeting card, or writing a short story. Compared to the non-prompted group, participants receiving self-regulatory scaffolds spent more time creating and felt more joyful during the process. Most importantly, they also produced works rated more creative by external judges.

Would it mean that promoting people's self-regulatory approaches makes them more willing to engage in creative activities more generally? While compelling evidence for this causal logic is yet to be demonstrated, some existing findings make such a prediction quite likely. Looking beyond the creative task performance, creative self-regulation explained a unique portion of the variance in the intensity of creative activities and attainments when personality was controlled for (Ivcevic et al., 2023; Zielińska et al., 2025). Moreover, people who rely on self-regulatory tactics during creative actions are more enthusiastic about their future creative engagement and are more committed to investing their time and resources in creative opportunities, such as professional assessments and training of their creative skills (Zielińska et al., 2025). Study 2, presented below, taps precisely into these *agentic* effects of self-regulation on promoting creative activity.

The Complexity of Agency–Activity Relationships

Empirical tests of the causal links between creative self-regulation, confidence, and engagement pose challenges, especially in naturalistic settings. Consider the effects of regulatory efforts on the intensity of engaging in creative actions. Well-designed training programs aimed at fostering self-regulation in everyday contexts, such as those developed for SRL (Ferreira et al., 2015; Schmitz & Perels, 2011), are typically embedded in specific activities or subject domains: people need a context or a goal-directed task for their self-regulatory efforts.

Supporting creative self-regulation in a similar way—during a particular creative activity—and expecting it to enhance overall daily creative engagement is demanding, as it requires between-domain or between-activity transfers. However, research has shown that the structure of creative self-regulation is invariant across domains (even though the mean levels of specific mechanisms may

differ; Zielińska et al., 2025). This suggests that once self-regulation skills are learned and practiced in one activity, they may also help people become more effective at initiating and sustaining engagement in other creative pursuits. Such self-regulatory scaffolding may equip students with transferable strategies—like planning steps, managing time, or monitoring progress—which can be applied across contexts, thereby increasing creative engagement beyond the domain of the original training.

Importantly, developing self-regulatory competencies might also enhance people's confidence to tackle challenges effectively. Previous research has even used simple strategy instructions as an experimental method to increase task-related efficacy beliefs (Locke et al., 1984). By planning their work, monitoring the outcomes and experiences, and reflecting on their strategies, students are more likely to perceive their progress as the result of their own effort. The creative process thus becomes more self-directed, more comprehensible, and ultimately more manageable, hence strengthening creative confidence.

Although confidence gained through a successfully guided project or activity may not readily generalize to confidence in other domains, it can increase students' willingness to challenge themselves in new contexts. When reinforced by effective self-regulation, confidence may encourage students to take creative risks (Beghetto et al., 2021) and seek out further opportunities for engagement. In this sense, creative confidence may help mobilize creative behavior more broadly, even outside one's typical or previously practiced repertoire. Taken together, we propose that improvements in creative confidence may partially explain the effect of enhanced self-regulation on students' creative engagement, thereby serving as a mediator in this relationship.

The second hypothetical mechanism involves emotions. When the creative process is perceived as more manageable thanks to self-regulatory involvement, it can boost not only people's confidence, but also positive active emotions. This effect has been demonstrated in recent research, where participants who received self-regulatory guidance during a creative project reported feeling happier and more interested, indicating more effective management of emotional resources

(Zielińska, Lebuda, Czerwonka et al., 2024). Notably, such positive activated mood states form a favorable emotional surrounding for creativity in everyday life. Diary research consistently shows that people are more creatively engaged on days when they experience emotions like happiness and excitement—an effect observed in general (Conner & Silvia, 2015) and more professionalized samples (Benedek et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2022). Overall, these findings suggest that positive active emotions—alongside creative confidence—may represent plausible paths through which strengthened self-regulation contributes to increased creative engagement.

The proposed relationships, although theoretically sound, by no means exhaust all the mechanisms involved in the dynamics of creative agency. One element that adds to this complexity is the likely reciprocal link between confidence and self-regulation and their complementary effects on creative engagement (see also Wang et al., 2021, for how the related constructs of metacognition and interest may work in a compensatory manner when predicting learning engagement). While the causal relationship *confidence* → *self-regulation* is one of the tenets of sociocognitive theory (Bandura, 1991, 2001), empirical patterns and theoretical explanations are not always clear. Consider a recent study that showed that in the context of creativity, favorable self-perception might even be necessary for effective self-regulation (Zielińska, Lebuda, Gop, et al., 2024). But why would this be the case?

Explanations for the effects of confidence on self-regulation within sociocognitive frameworks often confound direct influences with the effects of past experiences. It is usually posited that more confident people are better self-regulators because of what they have learned and how they have capitalized on past successes and seized opportunities (Bandura, 1997). Yet, when framed this way, confidence beliefs seem to play an indirect role in the *past activity* → *self-regulation* link, rather than serving as the sole cause of self-regulation. In fact, such reasoning implies that confidence does indeed emerge from *successfully regulated activity*, suggesting a recursive dynamic rather than unidirectional relationships.

Empirically testing all the nuances of the relationship between creative agency and creative engagement extends beyond the capacity of a single (or even double) study and requires a comprehensive research program. Below, we provide an overview of two studies that disentangle some of these relationships, shedding light on the everyday dynamics of students' creative engagement. Figure 1 integrates the primary hypotheses tested across both studies with the broader conceptual framework outlined earlier.

Figure 1

Theoretical Relationships Between Elements of Creative Agency and Creative Engagement Tested in Study 1 and Study 2

Note. S1, S2 = specific variables measured in Study 1 and/or Study 2, respectively. Only the variables and relationships shown in color were empirically tested. Variables shown in white and dashed lines represent theoretically hypothesized components (see Beghetto & Karwowski, in press) that were not examined in the present research.

The Present Studies

This investigation examines the dynamics of agency–activity associations within the context of university students’ everyday creativity. By conducting two micro-longitudinal, data-intensive daily diary studies, we aimed to capture these links in students’ idiosyncratic and variable environments, demonstrating how their self-perception and self-regulation affect daily creative engagement. The two studies described below addressed different yet complementary research questions.

Study 1 explored the reciprocal relationships between creative confidence and everyday creative engagement. Following recommendations for inferring causal patterns in diary data, which have also been applied in creativity research (Conner et al., 2018; Karwowski et al., 2021), we used lagged analyses to determine whether creative activities undertaken by students on one day lead to positive changes in their creative self-perception the following day, and vice versa. We hypothesized (H1.1) that students’ engagement in creative actions would enhance their confidence, i.e., those who spend more time on creative pursuits will be more likely to believe they can generate original and valuable ideas. On the other hand, based on the premises of the CBAA model (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019), we also hypothesized (H1.2) that creative confidence makes them more prone to engage in creative actions the next day.

Study 2 shifted the focus to the understudied element of creative agency: creative self-regulation, testing its causal effects on both creative confidence and activity. This study employed an experimental design, with students either receiving self-regulatory scaffolds (experimental group) or not receiving any additional support (control group) during a long-term creative project. Along with daily measurements of participants’ work experiences, this design allowed us to address three specific questions.

Our first goal was to examine the links between self-perception and regulatory aspects of creative agency, particularly focusing on the benefits of self-regulation support for creative confidence. While the relationship between these aspects has been demonstrated in correlational research (Zielińska et al., 2022a, 2025), the causal links have received limited attention. Therefore,

we aimed to determine whether providing students with self-regulatory prompts, thus supporting them during the creative process, would elevate their confidence. This perspective could potentially extend the well-established tenets of sociocognitive theory (Bandura, 1997) by demonstrating that not only are confidence beliefs a building block of effective self-regulation, but teaching self-regulation also improves confidence. Although we hypothesized (H2.1) that creative confidence would grow among all students as they progressed in the project, we also hypothesized that supporting self-regulation would further enhance confidence compared to the non-prompted group (H2.2).

Second, we explored whether strengthening students' self-regulation during a particular creative process (here: writing a creative story) translates into overall higher daily creative activity. Should this effect be observed, it would indicate the effectiveness of self-regulation support in mobilizing creative engagement more generally, highlighting its agentic nature. Considering the likely domain-general character of creative self-regulation (Zielińska et al., 2025), such a transfer indeed seemed plausible, so our third hypothesis (H2.3) predicted that students receiving self-regulation prompts would demonstrate higher engagement in creative activities other than those used in the study.

If activating self-regulation during one activity does indeed lead to broader creative engagement, the mechanisms behind this transfer remain an open exploratory question, forming the third goal of Study 2. While any transfer across domains or activities is inherently complex and shaped by both intraindividual and contextual factors, we focused on two complementary mechanisms likely involved in the dynamics of creative engagement. First, we hypothesized that self-regulatory support would increase creative activity by enhancing students' creative confidence (H2.4). Broadening students' repertoire of self-regulatory strategies may help them perceive creative challenges as more manageable, thereby boosting confidence and, in turn, encouraging greater openness to new creative endeavors. Second, we hypothesized (H2.5) that the effect of activating self-regulation on broader creative engagement might also be mediated by increased levels of

positive active emotions. Building on previous research showing that self-regulation prompts make people more interested in the task in experimental settings (Zielińska, Lebuda, Czerwonka, et al., 2024), we aimed to replicate this path in our dynamic diary study. Given that creative confidence and positive activated feelings are likely interrelated, demonstrating that confidence predicts students' everyday creativity independently of emotional states would underscore its incremental validity and further highlight the role of perceived agency in everyday creative engagement.

Taken together, the two studies presented below explore the complex relationships between creative confidence, self-regulation, and creative engagement (see Figure 1). We drew on intensive daily diary data to capture the dynamic interplay of these components in university students' real-life settings. From an analytical standpoint, we selected approaches well-suited to handling the complexity of such data. Study 1, which focused on the reciprocal effects between creative confidence and everyday creative engagement, employed dynamic structural equation modeling (DSEM; Asparouhov et al., 2018; McNeish & Hamaker, 2020). DSEM is a flexible framework conceptually similar to cross-lagged panel models but more appropriate for intensive, frequent, within-person measurements. It allows testing the cross-lagged within-person associations among variables, while controlling for time trends and autoregressive effects. Consequently, DSEM is well-suited for analyzing diary data and exploring the assumed bidirectional links. In Study 2, we used multilevel models to estimate between-group differences (experimental vs. control) and within-person changes in creative confidence and creative engagement, while accounting for the nested structure of the data. In the following sections, we describe the methods and results of each study in detail.

Study 1

Method

Participants

Two hundred seventy-nine students from two Polish universities took part in the study. Participation was voluntary, and all students who agreed to participate in a month-long study in exchange for

course credits were invited. However, participants who completed less than seven diaries ($N = 45$, $M_{\text{diaries}} = 1.58$, $Me_{\text{diaries}} = 1$) were excluded from the analyses (see, e.g., Conner & Silvia, 2015; Zielińska et al., 2022b), yielding a final sample of 234 (92% females; $M_{\text{age}} = 21.21$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 2.70$). The total number of Level-1 data (*days x person*) was 5923; on average, participants responded to 25 of 31 diaries ($Me_{\text{diaries}} = 28$; 81% response rate).

Measures

Creative Confidence. Every day, we measured participants' creative confidence with a single item asking: "To what extent did you feel today like a person who is creative, generating original and useful ideas?" Participants responded on a 7-point Likert scale from 1 = *not at all* to 7 = *very much*.

Creative Engagement. To capture the different forms that students' everyday creative engagement might take, we operationalized it in two ways: by asking about specific creative activities undertaken during the day and about students' subjective perception of having done something creative.

Subjective Creative Behavior. Participants answered a single question about their self-perceived creative behavior during the day: "Did you do anything today that required creative thinking or using your imagination?" Answers were provided daily using a binary *yes* = 1 and *no* = 0 scale. This single-item binary measure has been effectively used in previous diary and ecological momentary assessment (EMA) studies on everyday creativity (Karwowski et al., 2017; Silvia et al., 2014; Zeitlen et al., 2022). While particularly well-suited for intensive measurement, helping to reduce the burden of repeated survey completion, it has clear limitations. One such limitation is that participants rely on their own implicit assumptions to determine what qualifies as creative behavior. Given how varied and diverse everyday creativity can be (Silvia et al., 2023; see also Villanova & Cunha, 2020), this approach can be considered valid (Kaufman, 2019). However, to gain a more detailed picture of students' daily creative engagement, we complemented this measure with a more fine-grained assessment of creative activities (see below).

Daily Creative Activity Across Domains. Students rated the intensity of their engagement in 15 different creative activities every day (e.g., creating entries for internet blogs and social media, taking photos, or cooking something according to their own recipe), using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *not at all*, 5 = *very intensely*). The activities were adapted from previous studies (Karwowski et al., 2017; Zielińska, Lebuda, & Karwowski, 2022) and are presented in Appendix, Table A1.¹

Given our interest in students' daily creative engagement, we computed an overall score representing the intensity of various creative activities. Although the average scores were low for some activities (see Appendix, Table A1), suggesting they were generally less relevant for students, we retained all items to have a composite that reflects the diversity of students' creative experiences. Also, the relatively low levels of creative engagement assessed using a specific, predefined list of activities are consistent with previous research, including both more static, correlational studies (Diedrich et al., 2018) and dynamic, measurement-intensive designs (e.g., Zhang et al., 2024).

The internal consistency of the 15 items was assessed using a 2-level omega composite reliability (Geldhof et al., 2014). The reliability was good at the between-person level ($\omega_{\text{between}} = .78$) but lower at the within-person level ($\omega_{\text{within}} = .38$). However, this is not uncommon in dynamic, micro-longitudinal research, especially when employing brief scales that aim to capture broad dimensions (see, e.g., Sun et al., 2020; Sun & Vazire, 2019; Wilson et al., 2017) and are often designed to prioritize validity over internal reliability (Gosling et

¹ An anonymous reviewer has rightly noted that the activities we asked about can be conducted in a way that is not necessarily creative, e.g., entirely routinely. Indeed, we acknowledge that engaging in different activities tells little about whether they were fulfilled in a novel or efficient way. At the same time, however, such a way of measuring people's activity appears quite typical in the psychology of creativity (see, e.g., Karwowski et al., 2017; Zielińska et al., 2022b). More specifically, scales measuring creative activity (e.g., Diedrich et al., 2018) or behaviors (e.g., Ivcevic & Mayer, 2009) do not ask explicitly about how activities are conducted (i.e., the creative or uncreative way of fulfilling certain behaviors), but rather about intensity or frequency of such behaviors.

al., 2003). Therefore, we calculated a composite score by averaging the daily scores from the 15 creative activities.

Procedure

After volunteering to participate in the study, students were informed about the research procedures and completed the informed consent form. The study lasted 31 days and was conducted online, with diaries provided daily via a survey platform and accessible for the students between 6 p.m. and midnight. Each diary included a self-report section, where participants completed the measures of creative confidence and creative engagement (i.e., subjective creative behavior and participation in specific daily creative activities).

Students were also given brief reflective prompts, described as homework for the next day (see Zielińska et al., 2022b, for a similar procedure). The prompts were intended to make the participation more engaging and to maintain students' motivation. The prompts either focused on students' creative agency (13 out of 29 prompts, e.g., *Think about yourself and your qualities for a moment. Which ones would you like to develop to become an even more creative person than you already are? List these qualities and plan how to strengthen and develop them*) or encouraged students' divergent thinking (16 out of 29 prompts, e.g., *Did you know that hugging a tree is forbidden in China, or that you cannot chew gum in Singapore? If you could introduce three new, previously unknown bans, what would they be?*). Two exceptions were made: on the first day, no additional prompts were provided, allowing the students to become familiar with the study's technical details; on the last day, instead of delivering prompts, we asked the students about their overall impression of participating in the study. The Supplementary Online Material [SOM] Table S1 presents the complete list of prompts used.

Analytical Approach

We analyzed the data using dynamic structural equation models (DSEM), a framework that integrates time-series, multilevel, and structural equation modeling, making it well-suited for intensive longitudinal data (Asparouhov et al., 2018; Hamaker et al., 2018). Models were estimated in Mplus

(version 8.11) using Bayesian Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC), which effectively handles the complexity of DSEM (McNeish & Hamaker, 2020). A default of two MCMC chains was used, and we requested 10,000 iterations to ensure stable posterior estimates.

We specified two models to examine lagged and cross-lagged effects between daily creative engagement and next-day creative confidence, and vice versa. The first model involved creative engagement assessed via a single daily item asking whether the participant did something creative that day. The second model used a broader index of daily creative activities. To test the cross-lagged effects of daily creative activity on next-day creative confidence, we regressed today's creative confidence (t_0) on previous-day creative activity ($t-1$), controlling for previous-day confidence ($t-1$; autoregressive effect or "inertia"). To examine the reversed direction, we regressed today's creative activity (t_0) on previous-day creative confidence ($t-1$) and previous-day activity ($t-1$). Both models controlled for time trends (i.e., changes in mean levels across days) and included a dichotomous weekend indicator (0 = weekday, 1 = weekend).

The models included random intercepts and random slopes at the person level (Level-2). Specifically, we estimated random intercepts for both creative confidence and creative activity. At the within-person level (Level-1), we modeled autoregressive and cross-lagged effects (lag-1) for both variables. These effects were allowed to vary across people by specifying random slopes for the autoregressive paths (e.g., creative confidence on previous-day confidence) and cross-lagged paths (e.g., confidence on prior-day activity, and vice versa). Linear time trends and weekend effects were also included, with random slopes for trends (across study days) and fixed effects for weekends. The DSEM framework thus allowed both within-person temporal dynamics and between-person heterogeneity in those dynamics to be captured. In a model predicting binary subjective creative behavior, we estimated a categorical DSEM using a probit link function (McNeish et al., 2024). Full model specifications and Mplus input files are available on the Open Science Framework (OSF) Repository (<https://osf.io/cw3ju/>).

We examined Potential Scale Reduction (PSR) to evaluate nonconvergence, with values close to one suggesting successful convergence. 95% credibility intervals (CIs) were used to assess whether model parameters were significantly different from zero (Asparouhov & Muthén, 2020). To evaluate the magnitude of the cross-lagged effects, we used the within-person standardized results provided by Mplus. Specifically, fully standardized coefficients are reported for most variables, while Y-standardized coefficients are reported for effects where the binary subjective creative behavior variable serves as a predictor.

As an additional robustness check, we estimated analogous models using Bayesian multilevel regression implemented in the brms package in R (Bürkner, 2017, 2018, 2021). This approach allowed us to account for the specific distributional characteristics of our outcome variables and to cross-validate the findings obtained in Mplus. Notably, it enabled the use of model specifications not currently available in Mplus's DSEM framework, such as zero-inflated (hurdle) models. These models were particularly useful for addressing the distribution of daily creative activity scores, which—consistent with prior research (Diedrich et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2024)—were positively skewed (skewness = 1.53; kurtosis = 3.45) and clustered at the minimum value. A substantial portion of participants reported no creative activity on a given day, resulting in a zero-inflated distribution. These complementary analyses largely supported the primary DSEM results and are presented in SOM Table S2. For the DSEM analyses, we applied a log transformation to the creative activity scores, which reduced skewness (skewness = 0.78; kurtosis = 0.29).

Results

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics and correlations calculated at the day-level and between-person level. Students' creative self-perception was positively and robustly related to creative activity variables at both the day- and person-levels. Also, all variables had substantial within-person variability, as indicated by robust 1-ICC (intraclass correlation coefficient) values.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics and Correlations Among Study 1 Variables

Variable	Day-level		Person-level		Creative Confidence	Subjective Creative Behavior	Daily Creative Activity
	M	SD	M	SD			
Creative Confidence	4.26	1.64	4.25	1.01	(.35)	.73	.57
Subjective Creative Behavior	0.63	0.48	0.62	0.29	.68	(.49)	.62
Daily Creative Activity	0.28	0.24	0.28	0.18	.44	.63	(.57)

Note. Daily Creative Activity scores were log-transformed. Intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs) are on the diagonal (in parentheses). Between-person ($N_{L2} = 234$) Pearson’s correlations are above the diagonal. Day-level ($N_{L1} = 5912\text{--}5919$) correlations are below the diagonal; correlations involving Subjective Creative Behavior are polychoric. All correlation coefficients are significant at $\alpha = .05$.

Both DSEM models converged successfully, with PSR values of 1.03 (Table 2) and 1.04 (Table 3). Creative engagement on one day—assessed by the intensity of undertaking various creative activities (YX-standardized coefficient: $\beta = .067$, 95% CI [.034, .098]) and the subjective feeling of doing something creative (Y-standardized coefficient: $\beta = 0.170$, 95% CI [0.126, 0.208])—significantly predicted the next day’s creative confidence. However, we found no evidence for the reverse direction: creative confidence on one day did not translate into higher engagement in specific creative activities or subjective creative behavior the following day (i.e., 95% credible intervals for these cross-lagged effects included zero). Thus, while creative confidence and activity were linked at the same-day level, the cross-lagged effects appeared unidirectional: creative engagement boosted next-day confidence, but higher confidence did not, in turn, increase next-day creative activity or subjective creative engagement.

Table 2*Unstandardized fixed and random effects from the DSEM with Creative Confidence and Subjective Creative Behavior*

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Fixed Effects (Means)</i>			<i>Random Effects (Variances)</i>		
	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>95% CI: Lower</i>	<i>95% CI: Upper</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>95% CI: Lower</i>	<i>95% CI: Upper</i>
Creative Confidence (CC) intercept	4.390	4.255	4.529	0.795	0.624	1.006
Subjective Creativity (SC) threshold	-0.554	-0.716	-0.394	0.647	0.382	0.967
Autoregressive effects						
CC (t-1) → CC (t)	0.084	0.045	0.125	0.017	0.006	0.030
SC (t-1) → SC (t)	0.357	0.277	0.438	0.033	0.002	0.068
Cross-lagged effects						
SC (t-1) → CC (t)	0.206	0.153	0.259	0.006	0.001	0.020
CC (t-1) → SC (t)	-0.019	-0.058	0.019	0.004	0.001	0.013
Time Trends and Covariates						
CC linear trend (days)	-0.008	-0.014	-0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
SC linear trend (days)	-0.003	-0.010	0.004	0.001	0.001	0.002
Weekend → CC	-0.011	-0.075	0.052	–	–	–
Weekend → SC	-0.090	-0.174	-0.007	–	–	–
Log residuals						
CC Variance	0.316	0.228	0.405	0.338	0.264	0.431

Note. Estimates represent posterior means from Bayesian dynamic structural equation modeling (DSEM). CI = 95% credible interval. Posterior distributions were based on 10,000 iterations using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) estimation with default diffuse priors, meaning results are driven by the data rather than prior assumptions. To account for unequal spacing of measurement occasions, we used the Mplus *tinterval* option with a 1-day time window. The intercept for Subjective Creativity (SC) equals the threshold with the sign reversed, on the probit scale. Residual variance for binary SC is fixed to 1 for identification and is not estimated. Boldface estimates indicate credible intervals that do not include 0 and are considered statistically significant. Weekend variable was coded 0 = weekday, 1 = weekend.

Table 3*Unstandardized fixed and random effects from the DSEM with Creative Confidence and Creative Activity*

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Fixed Effects (Means)</i>			<i>Random Effects (Variances)</i>		
	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>95% CI: Lower</i>	<i>95% CI: Upper</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>95% CI: Lower</i>	<i>95% CI: Upper</i>
Creative Confidence (CC) intercept	4.375	4.231	4.520	0.887	0.714	1.106
Daily Creative Activity (CA) intercept	0.315	0.290	0.341	0.034	0.027	0.042
Autoregressive effects						
CC (t-1) → CC (t)	0.120	0.085	0.155	0.018	0.008	0.032
CA (t-1) → CA (t)	0.151	0.113	0.190	0.013	0.003	0.026
Cross-lagged effects						
CA (t-1) → CC (t)	0.547	0.252	0.790	0.198	0.013	0.731
CC (t-1) → CA (t)	-0.002	-0.007	0.003	0.001	0.001	0.001
Time Trends and Covariates						
CC linear trend (days)	-0.006	-0.012	-0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
CA linear trend (days)	-0.003	-0.004	-0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000
Weekend → CC	-0.014	-0.077	0.049	-	-	-
Weekend → CA	0.000	-0.007	0.007	-	-	-
Log residuals						
CC Variance	0.349	0.263	0.432	0.325	0.256	0.415
CA Variance	-4.092	-4.195	-3.990	0.533	0.430	0.663

Note. Estimates represent posterior means from Bayesian dynamic structural equation modeling (DSEM). CI = 95% credible interval. Posterior distributions were based on 10,000 iterations using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) estimation with default diffuse priors, meaning results are driven by the data rather than prior assumptions. To account for unequal spacing of measurement occasions, we used the Mplus *tinterval* option with a 1-day time window. Boldface estimates indicate credible intervals that do not contain 0 and are deemed statistically significant. Daily Creative Activity scores were log-transformed. Weekend variable was coded 0 = weekday, 1 = weekend.

Discussion

How are students' creative activity and confidence related? On the surface, this question might seem trivial to answer, yet as our Study 1 demonstrated, these relationships are nuanced when reciprocal links are considered. In this section, we offer a brief summary and discussion of the crucial findings obtained, leaving the more in-depth interpretations of both studies' results for the General Discussion.

Thus, what are the confidence–engagement relationships? This large and long diary study shows that the nuances we mentioned might stem from the level of analysis (i.e., between- vs. within-person associations), the analytical approaches used (i.e., more static vs. dynamic, lagged analyses), and the creative activity measure applied (single-item subjective creativity vs. a scale that covers the intensity of conducting ten various activities). At first sight, the links between confidence and activity were indeed positive, robust, and consistent with previous literature (Tierney & Farmer, 2002). More creatively confident students engaged more intensively in creative activity, and—given that this between-person association was correlational—it went the other way around as well, i.e., active and engaged students were more creatively confident than their peers with lower activity. This pattern closely resembles previous correlational and longitudinal findings (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019) and speaks to Study 1's internal validity.

More interestingly and dynamically, the positive correlations were also observed at the level of days nested in participants. The days when students engaged more intensively in various creative activities were the same days when they felt more creative. This effect is also correlational, even if obtained at the within-person level. Day-level analyses of students' creative activity are rare in the literature. Similarly, although previous studies explored variability in creative activities in both students (Conner et al., 2018) and more professionalized populations (Smith et al., 2022), within-person changes in students' creative confidence have not been analyzed to date.

Overall, the links between confidence and engagement are positive and robust at the person and day level. What about their more dynamic relationships? The primary focus for Study 1 was on

lagged within-person associations; our H1.1 predicted that creative engagement would boost students' next day's creative confidence, and, in a similar vein, our H1.2 inferred from the CBAA model (Beghetto & Karwowski, in press; Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019) that confidence will lead to increased activity the next day.

The lagged analyses supported H1.1, i.e., creative engagement on one day was positively linked to confidence the next day, controlling for students' confidence the previous day. However, we did not find support for H1.2. At the within-person level, students' next-day activity was unrelated to their previous day's confidence. This is precisely where the more nuanced pattern occurs: confidence and activity are intertwined at the person- and day levels, but the lagged within-person relationships are less systematic. Previous activity builds confidence, consistent with sociocognitive theorizing and empirical evidence (Bandura, 1997; Sitzmann & Yeo, 2013), but confidence does not translate into the next day's creativity.

Strengths and Limitations

Study 1 findings should be interpreted in light of the strengths and limitations of this investigation. Strengths involve a relatively large sample and an extended study period. Also, our measurement of students' everyday creative activities across domains might be considered an advantage compared to previous diary studies that utilized only single-item measures of creative activity (e.g., Conner & Silvia, 2015). Indeed, although our creative engagement measures were related ($r = .68$ and $r = .73$ at within- and between-person, respectively), they did not refer to synonymous phenomena.

There are, however, also limitations that should be addressed in future studies. We emphasize five that warrant closer attention. While some apply to all daily diary investigations, others are more specific to our study.

The first limitation is the self-report measurement utilized in this research. Although typical and perhaps unavoidable in diary studies, using the same short questionnaires over a month comes with costs and validity threats—from boredom and fatigue to social desirability bias to acquiescence bias, to name a few. Given some recent dynamic studies that successfully used more objective

measures of creative abilities (Rominger et al., 2023), there is undoubtedly space for the less declarative measurement of students' creative activity. That might involve recording time spent on particular creative activities or collecting samples of products created. While logistically challenging, such an approach would seem particularly fruitful for future studies.

The second limitation concerns our restrained understanding of students' thoughts when they responded to our single-item measure of creative engagement ("Did you do anything today that required creative thinking or using your imagination?"). As shown, most participants (62%) declared doing something creative most days (63%). In contrast, their self-reported intensity of engaging in the activities listed on the creative activity scale was generally low and zero-inflated. This implies that there were certain creative behaviors (or behaviors students *considered* creative) that we did not cover in our creative activity scale. Hence, future studies would benefit from either more inclusive scales (which might be challenging in diary studies) or open-ended questions related to creative activities undertaken (Silvia et al., 2023; Zielińska, 2020).

It seems cardinal to better understand what students have in mind when they claim they did something that required using their creativity and imagination on a particular day. In diary or ESM studies, explicitly asking about the content of behaviors participants considered creative, although increasing the burden, might be particularly insightful. Given that students spend much of their time in school (or university, as in our case), one might speculate that those creative behaviors are likely learning-related, a hypothesis supported by significantly less intensive subjective creative behavior on weekends. However, a recent ESM study that asked students about their activities with an open-ended question showed that they might also feel creative when traveling, resting, getting ready and taking care of their appearance, shopping, or attending church (Silvia et al., 2023). Such direct measurements of students' activity are much needed to better understand their thoughts when they claim they did something creative.

The third limitation of this study is the sample's composition. The majority of participants were female students, which, although typical for psychology and education majors, might have

influenced the intensity of specific activities undertaken, particularly given some well-established sex-specific preferences in creative domains (Elisondo, 2021). Quite naturally, studies involving more balanced proportions of men and women are needed to test the generalizability of these findings.

Fourth, we acknowledge the limited within-person reliability of our creative activity measure. While sufficiently reliable at the between-person level (i.e., people who reported engagement in one activity tended to be more involved in other activities, resulting in the positive average correlation at the between-person level), within-person reliability was mediocre. Although this is typical when broad constructs are measured with short scales on a daily level (Sun & Vazire, 2019; Wilson et al., 2017), such reliability makes it challenging to detect weaker effects due to increased error variance. Still, we believe such lower reliability was (and is) somehow unavoidable. Recall that our creative activity measure involved fifteen activities that could be mapped into various domains. People are unlikely to demonstrate the increased intensity of creating entries for a blog, taking photos, and cooking precisely on the same day. After all, days' length cannot be stretched, and the more effort put into one activity, the less time there is for the others. This trade-off at the day level naturally limits intercorrelations—and, hence, internal consistency—as long as diversified activities are included, which was our case.

Fifth and finally, despite our attempts to encourage students' creative engagement by providing daily prompts, the overall activity level participants declared was low, at least in terms of the fifteen activities we asked about in our creative activity scale. This zero-inflated distribution, typical in creativity literature (Rodriguez et al., 2023; Silvia et al., 2012), when paired with moderate day-to-day variability, might again limit our ability to detect more negligible effects. Related to this point, our prompts were domain-general and did not require students' intensive engagement. In fact, both creative confidence and creative activity—but not subjective feeling of being creative—tended to decline over time (see Tables 2 and 3). Consequently, it seems vital to analyze the links between creative confidence and activity when participants face a more specific situation requiring creativity. It might be a problem-solving challenge, drawing, or composing something. Situating self-perception

and activity within a particular task or set of tasks—the same for all participants—might reveal even more specific relationships. This was precisely why, in our preregistered dynamic and experimental Study 2, students' confidence and activity were measured in the context of a long-term creative writing task.

Study 2

Method

Participants

Study 2 consisted of two parts: a primary daily diary investigation and a follow-up conducted a month later. One hundred twenty-nine university students participated in the daily diary portion, which involved preparing a creative project (medium-length written story; see Procedure section for details). Students were offered course credits for their participation, and all who volunteered were invited. In line with our preregistration (https://aspredicted.org/8PK_LFD), we excluded participants who did not provide a draft of their creative project and completed fewer than five diaries ($N = 1$). The final sample for the daily diary portion comprised $N = 128$ students (86% women, 12% men, 2% nonbinary) aged 19-37 ($M = 21.0$, $SD = 2.52$). The total number of day-level data (*days x person*) was 2399; on average, participants responded to 19 of 21 diaries ($M_{\text{diaries}} = 20$; 90% response rate).

In the follow-up, a total of $N = 146$ students participated. This included $N = 111$ students who had taken part in the daily diary portion (87% follow-up response rate), and an additional comparison group of $N = 35$ students who had not participated in the diary component.

Measures

Project-Related Measures. During the three weeks of working on the project, participants completed short daily diaries about their experiences related to working on the story that day. Each diary asked about various aspects of daily work, including:

Creative Confidence. Similar to Study 1, participants' creative confidence was measured with a single item asking to what extent they felt like a person who is creative and able to

generate original and valuable ideas while working on the project. Students responded on a 10-point Likert scale from 1 = *not at all* to 10 = *very much*.

Task-Specific Creative Self-Efficacy. We used a state-like creative self-efficacy (CSE) measure to capture participants' conviction that they can handle the project and provide original work as the final outcome. Participants answered three questions each day: (1) "How confident are you in your ability to handle this project?" (2) "How confident are you that your working style allows you to create something creative?" (3) "How confident are you that what you ultimately present will be creative?" and responded using a 0-100% slider. Responses to these three questions were highly correlated ($\omega_{\text{between}} = .97$, $\omega_{\text{within}} = .84$) and averaged for an aggregate score.

Emotions. Participants rated how intensely they felt each of the eight listed emotions selected from the previous investigation (Zielińska, Lebuda, & Karwowski, 2022) based on their factor loadings to encompass positive active, negative active, negative passive, and emotionally mixed experiences. A 10-point Likert scale was used, ranging from 1 = *not at all* to 10 = *very intensively*.

A parallel analysis suggested a three-factor solution for emotions (see SOM Table S3, Figure S1 for detailed results), with clear negative passive and negative active emotion factors. However, one larger factor suggested a combination of *happy*, *joyful*, *surprised*, and *interested* emotions. Given the slightly lower factor loading for the *surprised* item and its different interpretation in previous studies (Zielińska et al., 2022b), we decided to remove it from the factor of positive active emotions. Consequently, average scores were computed to represent positive active (i.e., *happy*, *joyful*, *interested*; $\omega_{\text{between}} = .96$, $\omega_{\text{within}} = .81$), negative active (i.e., *annoyed*, *frustrated*; $\omega_{\text{between}} = .97$, $\omega_{\text{within}} = .77$), and negative passive (i.e., *dull*, *besotted*; $\omega_{\text{between}} = .96$, $\omega_{\text{within}} = .66$) emotions, while the one-item feeling of *surprise* was analyzed separately.

Daily Creative Activity. All participants rated the intensity of their engagement in 14 creative activities every day—the same as in Study 1—using a 10-point Likert scale (1 = *not at all*, 10 = *very intensively*). Given the character of the creative projects students worked on, we excluded one item used previously, as it was explicitly related to story writing, thus not capturing a creative activity beyond project engagement (i.e., *writing, e.g., poems, short stories, novels, plays*). An aggregate daily creative activity measure was computed as the average of the 14 items ($\omega_{\text{between}} = .77$, $\omega_{\text{within}} = .43$; see Appendix, Table A1, for the full list of items). As in Study 1, the obtained scores were positively skewed (skewness = 1.65; kurtosis = 3.81); thus, we applied a log-transformation, which reduced the skewness (skewness = 0.73; kurtosis = -0.14)².

Future Creative Engagement. A month after the story writing project, in a separate study, students were asked to imagine they were novel writers and rate how likely they were to write a novel someday. Participants answered three items using a 0-100% slider, asking how likely it is that they (1) “will actually write a novel someday,” (2) “could create a novel that is unlike any other,” and (3) “could come up with a captivating, original storyline as the basis for the book’s plot.” The responses for the three questions were highly interrelated ($\alpha = .81$) and averaged.

Procedure

The study was preregistered (https://aspredicted.org/8PK_LFD). Students who volunteered to participate in the story-writing project were informed about the study’s goals and procedures and provided informed consent. A few days later, the 21-day procedure began, consisting of two main components: (1) working on the creative project and submitting the effects once a week via an online survey, and (2) sharing the work experiences through daily diaries. Participants were randomly assigned to one of two conditions: control (N = 66) and experimental (N = 62). The experimental

² As in Study 1, a substantial portion of scores clustered at the minimum value, producing a zero-inflated distribution. Thus, we additionally ran hurdle models to better account for the nature of this data. These analyses are detailed in SOM Table S7 and largely replicate the findings presented in the main text. We selected the log-transformed scores as our primary analytical approach, as it was more suitable for the mediation analyses conducted—analyses that are not straightforward to apply or interpret within the hurdle modeling framework.

group received simple prompts embedded in their daily diaries to encourage self-regulatory engagement while working on the project.

Over three weeks (i.e., 21 days), participants from both the control and experimental groups worked on a project requiring them to write a story. The scope and topic of the project were flexible, but to give students a sense of direction, we instructed them to write a story approximately 7-9 pages long in standard manuscript format in the genres of fantasy, science fiction, or crime. Participants were prompted to be creative with their projects and to come up with stories that are original, interesting, unusual, or humorous (Nusbaum et al., 2014). Students were encouraged to work on their stories daily but were informed that work did not necessarily have to entail writing; it could also include seeking inspiration, gathering materials, or brainstorming ideas.

Each day, the diaries were provided online using the PsyToolkit survey platform (Stoet, 2010, 2017) and were accessible to the students between 7 p.m. and midnight. The diaries began by asking the students whether they worked on their stories that day. If the response was positive, students were asked for details about their work (e.g., what precisely they did, where they worked, and for how long), their perceived progress, task-specific CSE, emotions felt, creative confidence, and daily creative activity. If the students did not work on their stories that day, they were only asked about task-specific CSE and daily creative activity.

As part of the daily surveys, the experimental group received brief prompts designed to foster self-regulatory mechanisms while working on their story projects. These prompts came in various forms, but essentially, they encouraged students to (1) reflect on their work, monitor the strategies used, and consider alternative ways of dealing with the challenges of the process, and (2) set their writing goals using the strategies of mental contrasting and implementation intentions (MCII; Oettingen et al., 2012). The reflective questions, provided daily, were based on a recent creative self-regulation framework (Ivcevic & Nusbaum, 2017; Zielińska & Karwowski, 2021) and related empirical studies (Ivcevic et al., 2023; Zielińska, Lebuda, Czerwonka, et al., 2024). For instance, students were asked: “How do you imagine the final outcome of your work at this stage?

Consider which ideas are worth pursuing and which you want to replace. Perhaps you now have some new ideas that seem worth following?”. Students provided written responses to these prompts. The complete list of prompts is presented in the SOM Table S4.

Additionally, at the beginning of each week, students in the experimental group were invited to set their writing goals using MCII principles, which helped them formulate goals, recognize the positive consequences of achieving them, identify possible obstacles, and create “if-then” plans. Table S5 in the SOM presents an excerpt from the weekly goal-setting form. Participants in the experimental group also set small daily goals throughout the week to help them achieve their weekly milestones. Each day, they were prompted with an open-ended question: “Think about what you will do tomorrow to get closer to achieving the main goal you set for yourself this week regarding your work on the story. Plan exactly what you will do, where, when, and for how long. Make sure your goal is specific and achievable within the day. Write down your plan below.”

To make sure students in the experimental group implemented the daily prompts and engaged in the goal-setting activities, we conducted a fidelity check by reviewing all responses to these open-ended questions. Two raters independently assessed whether each response reflected sufficient engagement with the intended self-regulatory activities. Interrater agreement was high across all types of prompts: daily prompts ($\kappa = .90$), daily goal-setting ($\kappa = .77$), and the weekly-introduced MCII exercises ($\kappa = .91$). The proportion of responses flagged for insufficient engagement was low: <5% for daily prompts (38–42 out of 945), 3% for goal-setting (27–35 out of 1,116), and <4% for MCII exercises (5–6 out of 171). Importantly, these evaluations were conducted at the day level, and instances of insufficient engagement were rare and isolated, occurring on single days rather than reflecting any consistent pattern. No participant showed sustained disengagement, suggesting that the group maintained reflective engagement with the prompts throughout the study.

The control group received no self-regulatory prompts but was encouraged to work on their stories daily. Additionally, participants in this group were asked an open-ended, general question about their daily reflections to ensure a similar level of study engagement across conditions: “Please

write down your observations and reflections from today. They may, but do not have to, relate to your work on the story. Feel free to use this space however you like—it's your journal." Students responded regularly ($M_{\text{characters}} = 105.99$, $SD_{\text{characters}} = 154.21$ per day), suggesting that their diaries were not disregarded or treated superficially.

Analytical Approach

Apart from the between-subject manipulation this study utilized, our data had a hierarchical structure with days nested within students. Thus, we relied on multilevel analyses to adequately capture the repeated-measures design. Our analyses followed four steps. First, we ran a set of multilevel models to examine the between-condition differences and time-dependent changes in participants' creative self-perceptions and emotions. Each model initially included Condition, Day, and their interaction as predictors. If the interaction term was not significant and did not substantially improve model fit, we reran the model without the interaction term for parsimony and more straightforward interpretation. All models included random intercepts for subjects. Models with random slopes for Day failed to converge and were not considered. To accurately capture the intricate patterns of changes in students' experiences, we supplemented our analyses by visualizing the data using the *loess* function in R, which fits a nonparametric curve with LOESS regression (Cleveland et al., 1992), adjusting to the local characteristics of the data.

Second, we tested whether the effects of supporting self-regulation extended to students' daily creative engagement beyond story writing. We ran a multilevel model regressing creative activity on Condition, while controlling for the Day and including random intercepts for subjects. In the third step, we explored the mechanisms behind the observed relationships using multilevel parallel mediation models. Specifically, we regressed creative activity on Condition and Day, but also on hypothesized mediators: creative self-perceptions and emotions. Then, we utilized the *boot.mlma* function from the *mlma* R package (Yu & Bin, 2015), which performs bootstrap resampling to estimate indirect, direct, and total effects, providing robust confidence intervals for inferences. The number of bootstrap samples was set to 1000.

Finally, in the fourth step, we compared students receiving self-regulation prompts, those who were not prompted, or did not participate in the story writing project at all, on their perceived chances of writing a novel in the future—a measure we consider a proxy for their future creative engagement. We used ANOVA followed by post-hoc pairwise comparisons with Holm’s correction to quantify the between-group differences.

All analyses were conducted in R (version 4.3.0) using the *lmer* (Bates et al., 2015), *mlma* (Yu & Bin, 2015), and basic R packages. Data and scripts are available for reanalysis at the OSF Repository: <https://osf.io/cw3ju/>.

Results

Table 4 presents descriptive statistics and correlations among study variables calculated at the day-level and between-person levels. All measured variables had substantial day-to-day variability, with 1–ICC values ranging from 28% to 77%. However, students’ task-specific creative self-efficacy was relatively less dynamic throughout the study duration (1–ICC = 28%) compared to their overall feeling of being a creative person, which showed robust within-person variability (1–ICC = 57%), highlighting the conceptual distinction between the two.

As in Study 1, students’ daily creative activity was positively related to creative self-perception at both the day and person levels, although the associations with creative confidence were less consistent at the person level. Positive active emotions were associated with higher, and negative emotions with lower, levels of creative self-perception. Aside from their links with positive active emotions at the day level, the associations between emotions and daily creative activity were less consistent.

Table 4*Descriptive Statistics and Correlations Among Study 2 Variables*

Variable	Day-level		Person-level		1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.
	M	SD	M	SD							
1. CC	5.49	2.27	5.43	1.63	(.43)	.74	.12	.65	-.33	-.24	.21
2. CSE	6.34	2.27	6.30	1.98	.65	(.72)	.22	.49	-.34	-.33	.01
3. Daily Creative Activity	0.35	0.34	0.36	0.24	.11	.17	(.48)	.12	.13	.03	.09
4. PA	4.46	2.37	4.40	1.89	.57	.46	.14	(.53)	-.23	-.23	.37
5. NA	2.60	2.25	2.67	1.65	-.30	-.31	.06	-.25	(.45)	.79	.18
6. NP	2.40	2.05	2.47	1.60	-.25	-.28	.03	-.24	.64	(.48)	.20
7. Surprise	1.94	1.74	2.00	1.13	.18	.08	.08	.28	.15	.12	(.23)

Note. CC = creative confidence. CSE = task-specific creative self-efficacy. PA = positive active emotions. NA = negative active emotions. NP = negative passive emotions. Daily Creative Activity scores were log-transformed. Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (ICCs) are on the diagonal (in parentheses). Between-person ($N_{L2} = 128$) Pearson's correlations are above the diagonal. Day-level ($N_{L1} = 1187\text{--}2398$) correlations are below the diagonal. Bolded coefficients are significant at $\alpha = .05$.

We examined how students' creative self-perceptions—their creative confidence while working on the project and task-specific creative self-efficacy—changed over time and across conditions. Our analysis revealed that creative confidence, i.e., viewing oneself as a creative person, increased throughout the study among all students ($b = 0.06$, 95% CI [0.04, 0.07], $p < .001$; see Figure 2). While the effect of the condition was not statistically significant ($b = 0.54$, 95% CI [-0.03, 1.11], $p = .064$), the confidence interval suggests a possible trend indicating that students in the self-regulation condition tended to feel more confident overall than the control group (see Figure 2).

We also observed that students' task-related creative self-efficacy increased as the project unfolded ($b = 0.04$, 95% CI [0.03, 0.05], $p < .001$). The prompts further strengthened this conviction ($b = 0.77$, 95% CI [0.06, 1.47], $p = .032$), but this effect was evident during the first nine days of the project and started to vanish thereafter (the *Condition x Day* interaction effect was significant and negative: $b = -0.03$, 95% CI [-0.04, -0.01], $p < .001$; see Figure 2). Thus, while the experimental group showed higher confidence in their ability to handle the task creatively from the outset, the control group gradually built their self-efficacy as the project progressed. Eventually, as their efforts produced tangible results, the control group caught up with the experimental group.

We also found that participation in the writing project was more emotionally rewarding for the self-regulating students, as indicated by the between-group differences in positive active emotions. Our initial model included Condition, Day, and *Condition x Day* interaction as predictors. However, based on a visual inspection of the data trends (see Figure 2), we also considered a more complex model with a quadratic term for Day to account for possible curvilinear effects. This model indeed fitted the data better ($\chi^2(2) = 40.72, p < .001, \Delta AIC = 36.70, \Delta BIC = 26.60$). Both the linear ($b = -0.24, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.35, -0.12], p < .001$) and quadratic ($b = 0.01, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.00, 0.01], p < .001$) terms for Day displayed significant effects, suggesting that positive active emotions initially decreased, then leveled off, and eventually started to increase in the last week of the project (see Figure 2). Importantly, there was also a significant effect of Condition ($b = 1.25, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.30, 2.21], p = .010$), indicating that the self-regulation prompts made students more enthusiastic and joyful during their work on the project. There were no between-group differences nor *Condition x Day* interactions for negative active, negative passive, and mixed emotions (see SOM Table S6 for specific results). However, we found that negative active emotions increased with the project's duration across all students (the effect of Day was significant and positive: $b = 0.03, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.01, 0.05], p < .001$).

Note that the differences in creative confidence, task-specific creative self-efficacy, and positive active emotions observed at the very beginning of the project (see Figure 2) do not reflect baseline differences between groups. The first self-regulation prompts were provided to the experimental group on Day 1 (specifically, MCII exercises), and task-related creative self-efficacy was measured only after students had responded. Thus, engaging in goal setting appeared to immediately enhance students' efficacy beliefs. Creative confidence and emotions were measured starting on Day 2, after students had already begun working on the project and the experimental group had engaged in the Day 1 prompts.

Figure 2

Time Changes in Students' Creative Self-Perception (Creative Confidence and Task-Specific Creative Self-Efficacy) and Positive Active Emotions Across Control and Experimental Groups in Study 2

Note. The nonparametric curves were fitted using Local regression (LOESS). The shaded areas around the lines represent 95% confidence intervals. Thin dotted lines depict the linear regression lines of individual students. Dotted vertical lines indicate the days of story draft submissions.

How Does the Self-Regulatory Support Influence Daily Creative Activity?

To examine whether the effects of providing self-regulatory guidance extended to students' engagement in daily creative activities beyond story writing, we ran a multilevel model, regressing creative activity on the condition while controlling for the effect of the day. Throughout the study, the intensity of engagement in creative activities declined (see Table 5). Presumably, this decline was due to the increasing amount of time dedicated to the project as it progressed (see SOM Figure 2), suggesting a trade-off between engagement in story writing and other creative activities. However, there was also a positive and significant effect of the condition, indicating that the prompted students engaged more frequently in creative activities than their peers from the control group (see Table 5).

Importantly, students' creative self-perception and the positive active emotions they experienced while working were also associated with greater engagement in other creative activities (Table 5). On days when people felt more creative and happier, they engaged more intensively in a range of creative actions. Note that whereas creative self-efficacy was measured daily, creative confidence was assessed only on days when students worked on the project. Thus, although creative confidence and self-efficacy measures were highly interrelated ($r = .65$ at the day-level; $r = .74$ at the person-level), we decided not to compute an aggregate score from the two to account for their conceptual difference. At the same time, to avoid multicollinearity issues, we introduced creative confidence and self-efficacy in separate models. Both turned out to be significant predictors of creative activity, even after controlling for the effect of positive active emotions. Finally, the effect of the experimental condition remained significant across models.

Did our self-regulation prompts transfer into enhanced daily creative activity due to changes in students' creative self-perception? To explore this, we ran two parallel multilevel mediation models, each testing the indirect effects of the condition through two mediators: one aspect of creative self-perception (either creative self-efficacy or creative confidence) and positive active emotions. The indirect effects of using self-regulatory prompts on creative activity (estimated at the

between-person level) were significant for both creative self-efficacy ($b = 0.008$, 95% CI [0.002, 0.013]) and creative confidence ($b = 0.006$, 95% CI [0.001, 0.012]). Additionally, in both models, the bootstrapped confidence intervals for the indirect effects of positive active emotions either excluded zero—when creative self-efficacy was included ($b = 0.009$, 95% CI [0.001, 0.016])—or had a lower bound at zero when creative confidence was included ($b = 0.008$, 95% CI [-0.000, 0.016]), indicating a potential mediating role. The direct effect of condition on creative activity remained significant even after accounting for both creative self-perception and emotional factors ($b = 0.101$, 95% CI [0.074, 0.132] for the model with creative self-efficacy; $b = 0.104$, 95% CI [0.078, 0.136] for the model with creative confidence), suggesting partial mediation.

Table 5

Results from a Multilevel Linear Model Testing the Between-Condition Differences, Time-Dependent Changes, and the Role of Creative Self-Perception and Positive Active Emotions in Daily Creative Activity

Predictors	Creative Activity									
	<i>b</i>	95% CI	<i>p</i>	<i>b</i>	95% CI	<i>p</i>	<i>b</i>	95% CI	<i>p</i>	
Intercept	0.36	0.30, 0.42	<.001	0.21	0.14, 0.29	<.001	0.15	0.06, 0.24	.002	
Condition	0.09	0.01, 0.18	.027	0.10	0.02, 0.19	.019	0.10	0.02, 0.19	.021	
Day	0.00	-0.01, -0.00	<.001	0.00	-0.00, 0.00	.634	0.00	-0.00, 0.00	.666	
CC				0.01	0.00, 0.02	.023				
CSE							0.02	0.01, 0.03	.003	
Positive Active Emotions				0.01	-0.00, 0.02	.098	0.01	0.00, 0.02	.039	
Random Effects										
σ^2		0.06			0.05			0.05		
τ_{00}		0.05 _{participant}			0.05 _{participant}			0.05 _{participant}		
Model Fit										
ICC		0.47			0.51			0.51		
N		128 _{participant}			127 _{participant}			127 _{participant}		
Observations		2393			1185			1185		
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²		.025 / .484			.044 / .536			.054 / .539		

Note. CC = creative confidence. CSE = task-specific creative self-efficacy. PA = positive active emotions. ICC = Intraclass Correlation Coefficient. Condition is a two-level categorical variable with a control group set as the reference category. *p*-values for fixed effects were calculated using Satterthwaite's approximation and Confidence Intervals [CI] using the Wald method. Random effects: σ^2 = residual variance, τ_{00} = random intercept variance.

A Look Ahead: Differences in Future Creative Engagement

To examine potential longer-lasting effects of participating in the writing project, we conducted a follow-up study one month after its completion. In this follow-up, we asked the students to imagine themselves as novel writers and rate the likelihood that they would write a novel someday. We considered this measure a proxy for their future creative engagement. Given the changes in creative confidence observed during the writing project (see Figure 2), we were interested in whether these changes would endure and influence students' expectations about their future creative pursuits.

The sample included three groups: students who wrote stories with self-regulation prompts (i.e., experimental group: $N = 55$; 89% response rate); students who wrote stories without self-regulation support (i.e., active control group: $N = 56$; 85% response rate); and additional group of students who did not participate in the writing project (i.e., passive control group: $N = 35$). The inclusion of the third group allowed us to test whether the mere act of completing the creative writing project led to a higher student-assessed likelihood of future creative attempts, or whether the self-regulatory prompts were necessary to produce any longer-lasting effect.

The overall effect of group on novel-writing likelihood did not reach statistical significance ($F(2, 143) = 2.45, p = .090; \eta^2 = .03$), but some differences were apparent (see Figure 3). Students in the active control group ($M = 46.55, SD = 24.80$) and those who did not take part in the writing project ($M = 46.42, SD = 22.07$) provided nearly identical ratings ($t(89) = 0.03, p_{Holm} = .979, d = 0.01$). However, students from the experimental group ($M = 55.33, SD = 22.59$) rated their likelihood of writing a novel significantly higher than the combined other two groups ($t(144) = 2.22, p = .028, d = 0.38$). When examined separately, the differences appeared less systematic (experimental group vs. passive control group: $t(88) = 1.77, p_{Holm} = .160, p_{unadjusted} = .080, d = 0.38$; experimental group vs. active control group: $t(109) = 1.98, p_{Holm} = .149, p_{unadjusted} = .050, d = 0.38$), but we emphasize relatively small sample sizes, which may have lacked sensitivity to detect potentially meaningful effects. Overall, these findings suggest that the inclusion of self-regulation prompts may have

fostered more enduring changes in students' creative self-perception, making them more optimistic about future creative engagement.

Figure 3

Comparison of Students-Assessed Likelihood to Write a Creative Novel in the Future Between Writing Project Participants and Non-Participants

Note. The experimental group consists of students who wrote stories with self-regulation prompts (N = 55); the active control group includes students who wrote stories without self-regulation support (N = 56); the passive control group includes students who did not participate in the writing project (N = 35).

Discussion

The results of this investigation extend findings from Study 1 by highlighting the benefits of a strategic, self-regulatory approach during creative endeavors, broadening the typically self-perception-oriented perspectives on creative agency (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019). While research on the controllable aspects of the creative process often focuses on performance gains (Beaty et al., 2014; Frith et al., 2021), our primary goal was to explore the *agentic side* of self-regulation: its potential to stimulate creative activity and boost confidence beliefs. Our findings provided empirical

support for the hypothesized effects, underscoring the role of self-regulation in enhancing creative engagement.

Fostering Self-Regulation Boosts Creative Confidence

The first set of our analyses revealed positive changes in students' perceived agency as they progressed in the project (H2.1), but promoting self-regulation during this endeavor boosted their self-perception even more (H2.2). With time and effort invested in the activity, participants viewed themselves as more creative and strengthened their conviction to handle the project and achieve creative outcomes. We interpret this finding as corroborating results from Study 1, where today's creative engagement boosted tomorrow's confidence beliefs. Here, we replicate this result with a different analytical approach by demonstrating that with each day of involvement in a relatively demanding, longer-term creative activity, people grow in their self-perceived creativity and begin to trust their creative capabilities more.

Notably, the confidence boost was further increased when students received support in managing their activities more effectively. While it has been widely theorized that efficacy beliefs actuate self-regulatory efforts (Bandura, 1991, 2001; Schunk & Zimmerman, 2007; Usher & Pajares, 2008), the reversed relationship—where self-regulatory involvement enhances self-perception—is equally plausible yet understudied. Our findings provide support for this logic. Students who were prompted to plan, monitor, and reflect on their actions felt more confident than their non-prompted peers. Importantly, these changes appeared to have longer-lasting consequences: one month later, when asked about a more demanding creative challenge, i.e., writing an original novel, students whose self-regulation had been activated were more convinced of their future success than their peers (see Figure 3). In contrast, students in the control group, who also worked on a creative story but without additional guidance, rated the likelihood of writing a novel someday similarly to those who had not participated in the story-writing project at all.

Fostering Self-Regulation Promotes Daily Creative Activity

Apart from changes in students' creative self-perception, this investigation also examined whether stimulating self-regulation encourages engagement in everyday creative activities (Zielińska, Lebuda, Czerwonka et al., 2024). While previous correlational research has shown links between self-regulation and real-life creativity, causal effects are understudied, especially in dynamic and naturalistic settings. Our study addressed this gap, suggesting that students who received self-regulatory support during the creative project engaged more intensively in various everyday creative actions than those who did not receive such scaffolds (H2.3).

The increases in broadly operationalized daily creativity are striking, given the specificity of the project supplemented with self-regulatory guidance, i.e., writing a creative story. Yet, such a broader impact of activating self-regulation is consistent with the domain-general character of the mechanisms supported during the study (Zielińska et al., 2025). Additionally, since both prompted and non-prompted students engaged in project-related writing activity, the boosts in everyday creativity are not merely carry-overs or an *activity-fuels-activity* effect. Instead, by providing students with hints on how to better manage their creative actions, we made them more willing to engage in various small, everyday creative acts. But what are the plausible mechanisms behind this effect?

Our mediational analyses showed that supporting self-regulation drove creative activity partially because of increased confidence (H2.4) and positive active emotions (H2.5). Both were natural candidates for the hypothesized indirect effects due to significant between-condition differences discussed earlier, as well as theoretical and empirical premises present in the literature. Positive mood states that activate and foster approach motivation towards a goal, such as feeling joyful and interested, are robust and consistent predictors of enhanced creativity (Baas et al., 2008), also at the within-person level. On days filled with excitement, energy, and enthusiasm, people are more creative than usual (Conner & Silvia, 2015; Smith et al., 2022; but see Conner et al., 2018 for a discussion on more nuanced causal relationships). They also more eagerly think about the current creative project when in a positive, activating mood (Zeitlen et al., 2022). Moreover, self-regulatory efforts can drive such experiences, ultimately leading people to achieve more creative outcomes. A

recent study demonstrated that promoting self-regulation during mid-length creative projects enhanced the final results precisely through increased positive activating emotions (Zielińska, Lebuda, Czerwonka et al., 2024). We expected a similar pattern of relationships in the more dynamic context of students' everyday creative engagement and found empirical support for the hypothesized mechanisms: the effects of self-regulation activation on daily creative activity were partly due to enhanced joy and enthusiasm.

Controlling for the effects driven by positive active emotions, the unique indirect contributions via creative confidence are particularly important. This mechanism aligns with the premises of the CBAA model (Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019), while also showing that the confidence boost stemming from improved self-regulation independently explains enhanced activity, even when emotions are taken into account. This finding underscores the incremental validity of creative confidence beliefs and further highlights the role of perceived agency in students' everyday creative engagement. Note that creative confidence and positive active emotions were robustly related at both the day ($r = .57$) and person ($r = .65$) levels (see Table 4). Still, our results indicate that prompting students to self-regulate increases their engagement in creative activities by strengthening creative self-perception and elevating positive active emotions.

While our analyses highlighted two indirect mechanisms that might be at play when explaining the effect of self-regulation prompts on broader daily creative activity, a significant direct effect remained. This suggests that there are other, unmeasured factors driving the transfer from effective self-regulation in one specific activity (story writing) to general, everyday creative engagement. Indeed, the transfer of self-regulatory skills from one domain to broader contexts is inherently complex and usually discussed or measured in terms of performance gains: achieving better outcomes in similar or distant tasks (e.g., Raaijmakers et al., 2018). However, our study focused on a different phenomenon: students' increased willingness to engage in a variety of everyday creative activities. This makes the observed transfer particularly intriguing, suggesting that something about the activation of self-regulation—not fully captured by our measures of confidence

or emotions—may have changed students’ motivation, openness to new creative opportunities, and enthusiasm about initiating creative actions. One explanation would be that students became more effective at planning their creative activities and transforming these plans into actual behavior—an effect previously observed in experimental settings (Liu et al., 2023). Still, what motivates students to engage in such planning remains an open question. Future studies should not only replicate this effect but also unpack the motivational consequences of stimulating self-regulation in creative settings.

Strengths and Limitations

We encourage reading the findings summarized above in light of the strengths and limitations of Study 2. One of the most apparent strengths of this investigation is its design: dynamic, micro-longitudinal measurements embedded in the contexts of students’ daily functioning, combined with experimental, between-group manipulation. This dual approach allowed us to test the hypothesized links between creative self-regulation, creative self-perception, and creative activity, primarily evidenced in correlational research (Zielińska et al., 2025). Notably, the creative challenge we invited students to during the study speaks to the ecological validity of our results, bringing insights into how the observed patterns occur in students’ daily lives.

Another strength lies in our twin-track measurement. The investigation focused on specific aspects related to the writing activity students engaged in (i.e., CSE, emotions felt) as well as more generalized characteristics, capturing broader everyday experiences (i.e., creative confidence, daily creative activity). By using the same items to measure everyday creative activity as in Study 1, we were able to replicate and extend key findings, leading to more robust and consistent conclusions about the *agency-activity* links.

Finally, the practical implications of our results are among the most salient strengths of this research. Our study was, after all, an intervention—quite an effective one. Standardized mean differences across the full 3-week writing project period were estimated at $d = 0.24$ for creative confidence, $d = 0.21$ for task-related creative self-efficacy, $d = 0.38$ for positive active emotions, and

$d = 0.28$ for daily creative engagement³. While these effects are relatively small, they appear realistic and align with recent benchmarks for educational interventions targeting social and behavioral outcomes, including self-regulation and personal adjustment (Wilson et. al., 2025). A follow-up conducted a month later further supported this finding by providing a unique test of the delayed effects of the self-regulation support, potentially informing future interventional attempts.

This investigation shares some limitations with those outlined for Study 1. The first concerns a female-dominated sample, which calls for the replication on more gender-balanced groups. A few other limitations are common in dynamic, micro-longitudinal research that utilizes daily diaries or ESM methods. These include the reliance on self-report measurements (Conner & Silvia, 2015; Smith et al., 2022) and the use of brief scales to capture broad intraindividual dimensions, often resulting in relatively low reliability at the within-person level (Sun & Vazire, 2019; Wilson et al., 2017). This was also the case for the present research; similar to Study 1, it primarily related to the assessment of daily creative activity.

However, as previously noted, the lower consistency at the day level might be more of a feature than a bug, telling us more of an ecology of people's everyday creative engagement rather than a flaw in the measure's psychometric quality. People's creative interests can be pretty heterogeneous on a day-to-day basis: some focus on select activities, while others engage in various kinds of creative actions, earning the label of "creative omnivores" (Silvia et al., 2023). Yet, can a similar breadth of creative engagement be expected at the same-day level? Pragmatic reasons suggest this is unlikely: even if small, little-c acts are considered, only a limited number can be squeezed within 24 hours, already filled with other activities and commitments. Thus, a wide variety of within-day creative activity appears improbable or would indicate a rather superficial engagement.

³ To quantify the effect of condition on measured outcomes, we calculated model-based standardized effect sizes using the *eff_size* function from the *emmeans* package (Lenth, 2023). These represent standardized mean differences (akin to Cohen's *d*), based on the estimated marginal means from the reported multilevel models. While we report standardized effects for interpretability, we acknowledge that estimating effect sizes in multilevel models is not universally agreed upon and remains an area of methodological discussion (e.g., Lorah, 2018).

More broadly, one might ask whether a single day is the most appropriate “time resolution” for studying phenomena like creative engagement. As both our studies and previous research on creativity in dynamic settings have shown, daily creative engagement tends to be low or null in the general population. While this presents methodological challenges, it also opens up a discussion on new directions for capturing creativity dynamics. One possibility is to continue using established methods (e.g., diary studies, ecological momentary assessment), but shift from fixed- or random-interval sampling (e.g., once daily or 5–9 times per day) to event-based or hybrid sampling approaches (see Silvia & Cotter, 2021). In such designs, participants respond only when a relevant behavior occurs (e.g., when they engage in something creative) or when their engagement reaches a certain threshold. This might help reduce clustering of responses at the minimum value and the resulting zero-inflated distribution, as seen in our study. Of course, this shift in focus would come at a cost—such results may be less representative of everyday functioning but could offer deeper insight into the here-and-now of creative activities. Another promising direction is to recruit samples that, while not necessarily composed of professional creators, consist of people who report high levels of engagement in creative activities (see Smith et al., 2022)—an approach also suitable for younger, student populations. This kind of preselection is likely to result in more varied creative activity scores, allowing for a more reliable examination of creativity’s antecedents and consequences.

General Discussion

Students’ creative abilities are beneficial for their learning (Gajda et al., 2017; Karwowski, 2022), well-being (Acar et al., 2021), and peer relations (McKay et al., 2017). Creative potential serves as a vital predictor of what students achieve in terms of their grades or standardized test results (Acar et al., 2024), and, as the last edition of the Programme of International Student Assessment (OECD, 2024) demonstrated, creative thinking is robustly related to math and reading skills ($r_s \approx .70$; see also Barbot & Kaufman, 2025; Kagan & Dumas, 2025; Weiss et al., 2025). Creativity and expertise literature (see, e.g., Benedek, 2024; Ericsson et al., 2009) emphasize that the path from creative potential to concrete and observable activities (not to even mention socially recognized

accomplishments) is a long and challenging one. Abilities matter, but clearly they are not sufficient for success.

Creativity can be theorized as agentic action (Beghetto & Karwowski, in press; Karwowski & Beghetto, 2019): behavior that requires initiative and decision to engage in uncertain endeavors supplemented by sustained motivation to continue and flexibly adapt to circumstances when problems occur. However, creative actions go beyond intrapsychological creative processes (Glăveanu, 2013), where cognitive mechanisms and skills play the leading role. Focusing on divergent thinking, remote associations, or analogies was very fruitful in understanding how people generate ideas in short-term tasks (Boldt & Kaufman, 2024), but explaining creative actions implies shifting the focus from people's cognition to their agency. This is why we analyzed the dynamics of students' everyday creative functioning and the role played by two aspects of their creative agency: creative confidence and self-regulation.

Creative Agency and Creative Action: Static and Dynamic Relations

Across two daily diary studies, we explored the role of students' creative confidence (Studies 1-2) and self-regulation (Study 2) in their engagement in day-to-day creative activities. Additionally, in Study 2, we manipulated students' self-regulation by either activating it or not, and examined how this activation translates into their confidence, task-specific creative self-efficacy, and engagement in creative activities beyond the focal task. In short, both our studies replicated between-person associations, showing that more confident students engaged in creative activities more intensively and—vice versa—those more active were also more confident. The same pattern occurred at the more dynamic level of days nested within participants; days with higher creative engagement were those when students considered themselves more creative, and the days with higher students' confidence were characterized by their intensified activity.

Apart from the replicable correlational patterns at the person and day levels, our Study 1 findings were less systematic when we analyzed lagged associations between confidence and activity. Creative confidence did not predict next-day creative engagement: neither when subjective

creative behavior, nor a broader index composed of particular activities, served as dependent variables. We did observe, however, that the previous day's creative engagement boosted the next day's confidence at the within-person level. These findings resemble well-replicated effects of academic achievement on confidence beliefs, along with more nuanced patterns in which changes in achievement are explained by confidence-related variables (Burns et al., 2020).

Our Study 2, when students worked on creative stories for three weeks, either with or without self-regulatory prompts, essentially replicated the main effects from Study 1 and extended them in the context of a particular creative task. We found that students' confidence and task-specific, dynamic creative self-efficacy increased in both groups when they progressed with the task, supporting the notion that engaging in something creative drives confidence. Yet we have also observed that confidence and self-efficacy were higher in the group that received self-regulatory prompts, showing causal links. Study 2 illustrated the benefits of activated creative self-regulation that go beyond the task at hand—transfer effects into other everyday creative activities (the same as measured in Study 1), which were mediated by creative confidence, task-specific self-efficacy, and positive affect. Finally, the positive effects of activated self-regulation lasted for quite some time; even a month after the study, students in the experimental group perceived their chances for accomplishing a creative project as higher than students from comparison groups. In what follows, we discuss these results in light of their implications for further theorizing and empirical endeavors.

Theoretical Implications for Creative Agency Theories

We discuss our findings in terms of their consequences for the theories of creative agency that are currently developed (Beghetto & Karwowski, in press; Zielińska, Lebuda, Gop, et al., 2024) as well as for the broader context of supporting students' creative functioning. First, we unpack and analyze the relationships between confidence and activity, particularly the within-person lagged effects observed in Study 1. Then, we offer some theoretically and empirically grounded explanations for why self-regulation might boost creative engagement. Third and finally, we dig deeper into self-regulation as an agentic “how to” factor that makes effective creative activity more likely and discuss

the role of identified mediators: confidence and positive active emotions in the link between self-regulation and activity.

Creative Confidence: A Cause or Effect of Previous Actions?

The sociocognitive theory postulates reciprocal relations between performance and confidence. Yet, while those links are robust at the between-person level, the direction of within-person relationships obtained in experimental or longitudinal designs is less clear (Sitzmann & Yeo, 2013). The path from performance to confidence is well-corroborated irrespective of design, albeit usually more robust at the between- than within-person level. However, the confidence-performance associations are less systematic, particularly at the within-person level (see, e.g., Beattie et al., 2011), with positive, negative, or null findings present in the literature (see Sitzmann & Yeo, 2013, for a meta-analysis). In Study 1, apart from significant correlational between and within-person relationships between those two constructs, our lagged within-person analyses showed that activity consistently predicted next-day confidence, but the reverse relationship did not occur. Study 2 replicated between- and within-person correlations of more general and specific confidence aspects (writing task creative self-efficacy) with students' creative activity.

The recent CBAA model, inspired by sociocognitive theorizing, postulates causal links between confidence and behavior. It hypothesizes that confidence grows due to various antecedents, among them, people's abilities, and further mediates the abilities-behavior relationship. Yet so far, CBAA was framed as essentially a between-person model, i.e., it theorizes that more creative people develop higher confidence, which translates into behavior and achievement. Naturally, within-person dynamics are relevant to this model's further development, with the within-person analyses presented in this paper being relevant to better understanding the mechanisms of the associations between creative confidence and behavior.

Confronted with between-person, individual differences-focused designs, within-person analyses might shed light on more dynamic, intraindividual processes. Thus, how did the previous literature explain the mixed findings regarding the within-person links between confidence (mostly

self-efficacy) and performance? When negative links are observed, the typical explanation refers to reduced effort people put in when their self-efficacy is high, especially when the task is considered easy (Vancouver et al., 2002). Indeed, allocating much effort to what is perceived as a trivial problem seems unnecessary and wastes an individual's resources. Yet, although this explanation might be accurate in the case of experimental studies with a specific problem or task to solve (similar to our Study 2), it does not seem particularly appropriate in the case of Study 1, when we followed our participants over a month and did not require them to focus on any specific problem, but instead monitored their typical day-to-day activity. The generalistic approach we took in Study 1 might make it more challenging to discover within-person changes and relationships. As discussed elsewhere (Bandura & Locke, 2003), within-person relationships between self-efficacy and performance may require specific contexts for people to improve their skills. Learning for an exam in school settings or working on a more extended creative project (as in Study 2) are better aligned with this requirement than the micro-longitudinal, yet still observational, conditions of Study 1. Although in Study 1, we found substantial variability in creative confidence and subjective behavior (and slightly less intraindividual variability for specific creative activity), the overall trajectory of changes in confidence and activity across the month tended to slightly decline.

Consequently, testing within-person relationships of creative confidence and performance might require experimental designs when participants can improve and develop. Another potential solution is applying experience sampling methodology, which is likely better suited to capture dynamic relationships than diary studies. We emphasize that this point refers not only to the method of potential future studies but also to the nature of the mechanisms involved. Recall that our within-person analyses examined whether students' activity on one day boosted their confidence the next day and vice versa. Although such day-to-day cross-influences are theoretically plausible, feeling creative might be driven by (and drive) specific situations and behaviors that occur during the same day. Apart from the benefits of within-person experiments, experience sampling studies with more

granular, intensive measurements of students' self-perception and behaviors might form a more appropriate design than in our Study 1.

Nevertheless, our two studies replicate previous findings regarding the links between confidence and action, including their causal relationships. Indeed, apart from robust between-person associations, we observed significant albeit weaker within-person *behavior-to-confidence* links. However, this was not the case for *confidence-to-behavior* relationships. Still, we should not too quickly dismiss the premises of sociocognitive theory and the CBAA model, which propose that confidence drives behavior. While Study 1 could not confirm this logic, some nuanced findings deserve a comment.

Specifically, our DSEM models showed the significant variability among participants in cross-lagged effects (see Tables 2 and 3). This result suggests that although the mean effect from creative confidence to creative behavior was negligible, some students had positive cross-lags while others had negative or near-zero cross-lags. These individual patterns, or latent profiles of relationships, warrant closer examination in future research. Importantly, this variability extends beyond the *confidence-to-behavior* link. It also applies to the reverse associations (i.e., *behavior-to-confidence*), the inertia of agency variables and creative activity (i.e., autoregressive effects), and time-dependent changes in the mean levels of these variables—all of which showed significant variability (see Tables 2 and 3). In sum, future within-person experiments and experience-sampling studies are necessary to provide more input into the within-person extensions of the CBAA model.

Does Self-Regulation Drive Confidence?

As argued in the previous section, the belief in one's capability to fulfill a creative task and a generally positive perception of one's creative abilities can energize real-life creative efforts. The two studies presented in this paper only partially supported this notion, echoing the well-established motivational role of efficacy beliefs for learning and academic success (Honicke & Broadbent, 2016; Murphy & Alexander, 2000). Previous literature often attributes this effect to underlying self-regulatory mechanisms: more self-efficacious and highly motivated people select, adjust, and apply

strategies that are more likely to lead them to a desired goal (Schunk, 1990). Indeed, a favorable self-perception may drive effective self-regulation, and conversely, low self-confidence might preclude any efforts. A recent study showed that a robust creative self-concept is necessary for achieving creative outcomes and employing effective self-regulation to attain them (Zielińska, Lebuda, Gop, et al., 2024).

However, the arguments for why confidence beliefs enhance self-regulation, reiterated in sociocognitive theories, pose questions worth further theoretical reflection. As noted in the introduction, it is often proposed that highly efficacious people draw on their previous, usually rich, experiences, recollecting strategies that worked in the past and using them to face current challenges (Bandura, 1997; Usher & Schunk, 2017; Zimmerman, 2002). This interpretation implies a reciprocal relationship between self-regulation and self-confidence, where enacted and successful self-regulation serves as a valid indicator of one's capability, which drives subsequent self-regulatory efforts. The *self-regulation-fuels-confidence* effect also aligns with the classic sources of self-efficacy, particularly mastery experiences (Bandura, 1997). Recognizing past accomplishments likely boosts self-efficacy, as does recognizing the methods that led to these accomplishments.

Inspired by this observation, Study 2 explored whether providing people with self-regulatory enhancements drives their confidence beliefs. This is exactly what our data showed: while all students strengthened their creative self-perception through continuous engagement in the creative project, those who received self-regulatory scaffolds were more confident overall. We see this effect as a valuable recasting of the classic sociocognitive interpretation of the *self-efficacy–self-regulation* link. Naturally, simultaneously testing the reversed relationship, wherein confidence increases self-regulatory efforts, would be insightful. However, it was not possible in this study due to the manipulation of self-regulation rather than its measurement. Effectively distinguishing between assessing and encouraging self-regulation is a nontrivial challenge, given that even simple, non-directive prompts, often in the form of reflective questions, can motivate regulatory engagement (Zielińska, Lebuda, Czerwonka, et al., 2024). Still, we see such an endeavor as a promising avenue for

future research to better understand the reciprocal links between creative self-perception and self-regulation, as well as their joint contributions to creative activity.

Self-Regulation-Driven Confidence as a Way to Prolonged Creative Engagement

One could argue that any further confidence boosts are redundant, given the already observed self-powered effect of sheer creative activity on creative self-perception. We concur with this notion to some extent, as confidence beliefs, especially when inaccurate and overestimated, might even be detrimental to one's efforts and demobilizing (Vancouver et al., 2002). Yet, this is precisely where the role of self-regulation might become crucial. Activity-driven confidence seems more tied to the immediate context and outcomes, making people more reactive to their current performance. On the one hand, this means embracing successes and progress; on the other, feeling discouraged by obstacles and difficulties, which may lead to abandoning efforts. In contrast, when people feel more capable through improved self-regulation, they are better equipped to deal with challenges: they understand that the process might not always be easy and persist in the face of difficulties, maintain motivation despite hurdles, and keep a positive attitude towards their goals (Ivcevic & Nusbaum, 2017). Indeed, as our study showed, while all students experienced ups and downs in their positive emotions while working on the project, the self-regulating group remained more enthusiastic about the process. Thus, we see the confidence boosts fostered by self-regulation as an effective way to promote more enduring, long-lasting creative engagement.

Our follow-up study supports this reasoning. When faced with an ambitious creative goal to be pursued in the future, i.e., writing a novel, students whose self-regulation had been activated rated their chances of success as higher than their peers. This finding partially addresses critiques of brief interventions aimed at evoking long-lasting changes (Moreau, 2022). Here, we demonstrate that even a month after the writing project, students who received self-regulatory guidance remained more optimistic about their future creative engagement. Simply working on the creative writing project, without additional self-regulatory support, did not yield the same effect: these students assessed their likelihood of writing a novel someday similarly to those who had not

participated in the writing project at all. Although the non-prompted group grew in confidence while working on their short stories, this increase was insufficient to bring about lasting change.

A few nuances to the observed effects of self-regulation prompts on creative self-perception merit attention. In the final stages of the creative project, the control group caught up with the experimental group in task-specific creative self-efficacy (CSE). This is understandable given that this measure, apart from its creativity-focused orientation, asked about the perceived chances to successfully finish the project, which was largely achieved by all participants. On the last day of the study, the vast majority of students (70%) considered their work finished when reporting on their perceived progress in the project.

A more general measure asking about seeing oneself as a creative person fluctuated more on a day-to-day level (1-ICC = 57% vs. 1-ICC = 28% for CSE), but the prompting effect was time-invariant: the group who received self-regulation prompts remained higher on this measure than the control group. This might suggest that while the task-specific CSE reflected achieving project-related milestones and systematic progress, a more general creative confidence, although embedded in the context of the project activity, captured an overarching sense of creative agency—more sensitive to daily experiences and reflections that go beyond the specific task being worked on. If this is the case, the persistent higher levels of confidence among participants who received self-regulatory support suggest that our prompts could also impact how students view their creative abilities more generally, potentially stimulating daily creative engagement. We found this precisely when testing how fostering self-regulation affects students' everyday creative activity.

Conclusion

These two micro-longitudinal investigations explored university students' creative activity in their everyday settings, focusing on the role of two elements of creative agency: confidence and the ability to self-regulate. Together, these studies demonstrated substantial variability in students' day-to-day creative self-perception and behavior (Study 1), along with robust correlations between confidence and behaviors at the person and day levels. Moreover, over a month, day-to-day within-person

changes in creative activity predicted the next day's creative confidence, while the reverse relationship, i.e., confidence predicting subsequent creative activity, was not supported. In Study 2, students worked on the creative writing project over three weeks and were randomly assigned to either the group that received self-regulatory prompts or the control group. Stimulating self-regulation boosted task-specific creative self-efficacy, general creative confidence, and positive active emotions. Strengthening self-regulation further transferred to greater engagement in various creative activities beyond the focal task, an effect partially mediated by confidence and emotions. Overall, this investigation demonstrates the benefits of analyzing students' creative actions in dynamic, behavior-related settings. It also provides one of the first attempts to integrate motivational, agentic factors into the exploration of students' creativity dynamics.

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Appendix

Table A1

Descriptive Statistics and Intraclass Correlation Coefficients Across Study 1 and Study 2 Creative

Activity Items

Variable	M	SD	min	max	Skewness	Kurtosis	ICC
Writing, e.g., poems, short stories, novels, plays	1.42	1.03	1	5	2.50	5.05	.46
	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Writing press articles, including, e.g., columns	1.09	0.46	1	5	5.71	34.64	.24
	1.09	0.69	1	10	9.33	95.35	.03
Writing research articles	1.25	0.77	1	5	3.33	10.52	.33
	1.13	0.79	1	10	7.33	58.90	.12
Preparing for public speeches	1.25	0.80	1	5	3.36	10.75	.29
	1.51	1.65	1	10	3.64	13.03	.18
Creating entries for internet blogs / social media	1.19	0.67	1	5	3.74	13.94	.43
	1.65	1.59	1	10	2.81	7.84	.41
Composing musical pieces, playing music	1.38	0.95	1	5	2.56	5.50	.51
	1.41	1.39	1	10	3.96	16.36	.40
Designing clothing	1.16	0.64	1	5	4.56	21.14	.39
	1.13	0.78	1	10	7.80	68.50	.12
Designing buildings, interiors	1.23	0.78	1	5	3.55	11.96	.42
	1.25	1.15	1	10	5.42	31.24	.17
Cooking something according to own recipe	2.21	1.51	1	5	0.77	-0.99	.45
	2.78	2.71	1	10	1.33	0.47	.35
Painting, drawing, sculpting	1.53	1.12	1	5	2.06	3.01	.40
	1.52	1.59	1	10	3.55	12.68	.36
Creating choreography, dancing	1.30	0.86	1	5	3.05	8.54	.43
	1.26	1.16	1	10	5.16	27.83	.55
Taking photos or filming, e.g., with a phone	1.98	1.35	1	5	1.09	-0.22	.40
	2.49	2.39	1	10	1.64	1.75	.30
Solving technical or scientific problems	1.47	1.00	1	5	2.13	3.47	.32
	1.80	1.91	1	10	2.66	6.51	.34
Programming or creating computer programs	1.04	0.34	1	5	8.76	82.90	.29
	1.08	0.60	1	10	9.52	100.70	.15
Creating websites	1.02	0.24	1	5	12.49	172.08	.27
	1.08	0.62	1	10	9.62	103.13	.14

Note. All descriptives were computed on day-level scores. Upper values pertain to Study 1, while lower values correspond to Study 2. The first item was excluded from Study 2; therefore, no values were presented for this item.